

Developing Leadership among Students through the Textbook: An analysis of the English for Today for Classes XI-XII in Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Good leadership is necessary for good governance and good governance complements development. One of the key conditions of development for a country is creating skilled and good citizens. The process of creating skilled and good citizens is a continuous one and is related to education policies and visions structured and implemented by different nations. In the educational institutions, textbooks often work as one of the most important tools and containers of national policies. This study is the analysis of English for Today for Classes XI-XII in Bangladesh from the perspective of leadership and building leadership skills among students. In this process of analysis, the study shows how the students are being viewed and considered as future leaders of a country. At the same time it also shows how different global and national education policies and documents focus and contribute to leadership development among students. Considering the textbook as the major document, this study discovers the leadership contents, categorizes different leadership types as reflected in the textbook and presents a perceptive discussion over the types with a parallel presentation from the textbook contents. As an analysis of an English textbook, the study also shows how Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) assists the practice of leadership building among students.

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1. Introduction

From a very simple sense, the word leadership would indicate such quality that inspires, guides and motivates others. However many researchers have defined leadership as an interactive process of social influencing towards a common goal (Bush, 2010). This 'common goal' from the perspective of Bangladesh can be identified as creating quality citizens through imparting quality education. The same has been echoed in the National Curriculum 2012 and the National Education Policy 2010 of Bangladesh. The National Education Policy 2010 intends to develop such citizens who have the skills relating modern and updated science and technology, and who would be able to contribute to eradicate poverty, illiteracy, corruption, communalism and backwardness and thus build up a developed and prosperous Bangladesh. To prepare the students of Bangladesh as global citizens and as skilled citizens it is imperative to develop strong skill among the students regarding English Language Communication because English is the language of global communication; the 'lingua franca'. "However, when English is chosen as the means of communication among people from different first language backgrounds, across linguacultural boundaries, the preferred term is English as a lingua franca"(House, 1999 & Seidlhofer, 2001 as cited in Seidlhofer, 2005). English as a 'lingua franca' refers to a way of communication in English among people who have different first languages (Crystal, 2012). First attempt of applied language teaching method was carried by Bangladesh Government in 1996 for the secondary level and in 1998 for the higher secondary level (National curriculum 2012) when the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) was introduced. Then it was redesigned in the curriculum of 2012. The curriculum of 2012 endorses need for learning English for communicative purpose. Communicative Language Teaching was introduced with a view to developing quality education focusing on creativity, critical thinking and lifelong learning. These intentions in the curriculum appear to be in line with the implications of the National Education Policy. So, the National Curriculum of Bangladesh, National Education Policy of Bangladesh and the purpose behind introducing and implementing CLT seem to appear in line with the idea of leadership as Sternberg (2007) identifies leadership as a combination of four crucial elements: leaders are creative, analytical, practical and wisdom-based. From here the importance of English Language Teaching (ELT) and development of leadership among students stand in parallel as the study is presenting the analysis of an English textbook which is taught in the educational institutions of Bangladesh following CLT.

In order to discover the existing idea of leadership from global educational policies and to identify the relationship among leadership, English Language Teaching and the textbook, this study first represents the analysis of global education policies and their relationship to developing leadership skills among students. Then it shows how CLT is associated with the ideas of leadership development. After that an analysis of different types of leadership is presented with a view to extracting leadership information from the EFT. Here it is very important to note that the types of leadership in this study do not directly fall after regular organizational leadership styles or types but indeed emerges from those. Leadership as a popular concept generally has continuously been discussed as an organizational phenomenon. Most popular leadership types have been theorized after Burns' concept of Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership (Eisenbach, Watson, & Pillai, 1999; Parry, 2002 as cited in Schimmoeller, 2010). Finally, the study presents a thorough analysis of the EFT and its contents, showing how far the contents associate the practice and development of leadership skills for the students. All of the analysis attempts are presented in the form of document analysis because document analysis can be a very reliable source of

information and provide researchers with clear ideas of the central phenomena regarding the research topic (Creswell, 2012). However, the major document analysis is the EFT for classes 11 & 12 focusing on the concept of leadership with a view to creating a significant impact on educational planning of Bangladesh. Whenever any research or study is done on any textbook, it creates opportunity for further qualitative improvement opportunity for textbook writers and curriculum designers on that very regard (Siddiqie, 2011). In order to know the existing condition of leadership lessons in EFT, the study reported in this article, intends to address the following questions:

- a. What proportion of the textbook contents is related to leadership ideas?
- b. What are the types of leadership discoverable from those contents?
- c. How these contents can help students build up leadership abilities?

2. Leadership and Global Education Policies

When searching for an understanding of the concept of leadership, Winston and Patterson (2006) unearthed 26000 articles from Expanded Academic Database in 2003. For them, it appeared to be quite similar with the story of the elephant and the blind men. The blind men went on to describe different organs of the elephant all of which were accurate yet not enough to understand the whole. So, this actually appears quite a big task to go for a definition of leadership. However they have tried to define leadership as combination of diverse gifts and skills. According to them, a leader who has leadership skills enthusiastically inspires his/her followers to achieve the organizational mission and objectives. When we talk about the global organizations working with education policies, their goals also appear to make the future generations skilled, sympathetic and empathetic. Standing on the verge of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, nations across the world have taken it as imperative to build up their future generations as leaders of tomorrow. Education policies across the world have been developed, planned and directed considering the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to be precise and specific concerning the SDG 4: 'Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all' (United Nations, 2015). To observe and realize the targets of SDG 4 global leaders declared "The Education 2030 Framework for Action" in 2015 in Incheon, Republic of Korea. Among the seven outcome targets of SDG 4, target 4.4 directly reads:

Beyond work-specific skills, emphasis must be placed on developing high-level cognitive and non-cognitive/transferable skills, such as problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, teamwork, communication skills and conflict resolution, which can be used across a range of occupational fields. Moreover, learners should be provided with opportunities to update their skills continuously through lifelong learning (Relationship between Sustainable Development Goal 4 and the Education 2030 Framework for Action, 2015, p.3).

Bangladesh is actively and vigorously contributing to the implementation of the Education 2030 Agenda. Bangladesh prepared its own post-2015 Development Agenda in line with the Education 2030 Agenda and set General Economics Division (GED) to lead in this regard and proposed for 11 goals along with 58 targets with corresponding 241 measurable indicators (Ahmed & Rahaman, 2016).

3. Leadership and CLT

The purpose of education should not merely to be transmitting knowledge; rather, it should inspire students to be the leaders of society, to use their knowledge base for the development of society. A policy should be opted by colleges and universities where they will focus more

on learning experiences which create leaders rather than hoping for such experiences to occur (Sternberg 2007). Teachers and educators must try to create a convenient environment for the students that give exposure to creativity and critical thinking which have been echoed in the National Curriculum 2012 and the National Education Policy 2010. By doing so the teachers can promote leadership environment for the students. It should also be noted that textbooks generally reflect ideas of national culture. While transmitting knowledge textbooks focus on political and social norms of a society. Social traditions, global history and traditions come under consideration while composing a textbook. The idea behind this is to make a student more socially accommodating and more conscious about his/her self esteem. UNESCO emphasized an international textbook to endorse equally a balanced proportion of knowledge, attitudes and skills. (Pingel, 2009). The English for Today for Classes XI-XII, generally being viewed as an international textbook incorporates the idea of developing knowledge, attitude and skill reflecting the visions of global education policies and the intentions of national curriculum of Bangladesh. It has earlier been discussed, mentioned and cited in this study how creativity, criticality and skill development have been addressed in the National Curriculum 2012 in Bangladesh especially in the portion of curriculum for English textbooks. The curriculum specifically opted for CLT with a view to skill development among the students. In terms of English teaching, CLT has the best possible way to come into effect to ensure a leadership practice among students. In English language classroom, creativity is ensured through productive skills such as speaking and writing. Writing seems to be more suitable for a little bit of older learners thus can be said for the college level students (Reid & Kováčiková, 2018). On the other hand critical thinking in an ELT classroom has threefold significance. First, it allows the learners to take charge of their own thinking. Second, learning experience becomes more expanded making learning more meaningful to the learners. Third, it highly correlates to learners achievements (Rafi, n.d. as cited in Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011). "Most important leadership qualities that should be brought to students according to the teachers' opinions are communication skills, problem-solving skills, responsibility, honesty, and goal setting, respectively" (Parlar, Türkoğlu & Cansoy, 2017. p.224). Interestingly CLT as an approach of English teaching, emphasized in the latest curriculum of Bangladesh, almost echoed the same idea. This has also been clearly mentioned and cited in the introduction chapter of this article.

CLT focuses mainly on communication and as an approach; it basically depends on motivating learners in order to build up communicative competence among them irrespective of any given circumstances (Papadopoulou, 2015). Communicative competence (Brandl, 2007 as cited in Papadopoulou, 2015) however, does not stand alone as a concept. It entails the advance of: **Linguistic competence** - which is the knowledge of vocabulary and grammar, **Sociolinguistic competence** - which denotes the ability to use specific language in specific contexts, **Discourse competence** - which signifies the ability to create and participate in a conversation in a coherent and cohesive manner, **Strategic competence** - which is the ability to solve communication problems when they arise. This is also widely recognized that CLT is prominently a student centered approach. The students are allowed to have their voices on the instructional decisions of the lessons (Brandl, 2007). Warm up activities, group works and project works done by students are major encouraging techniques of CLT. Warm up strategies suit perfectly in CLT as warm ups give the students a sense of belonging to the students. The students feel more at home. It helps them to increase their ability (Bucholz & Sheffler, 2009 as cited in Ponce, Macías, & Zambrano, 2020). Warm up activities are being highly regarded and recommended to engage the students in the classrooms as Velandia (2008) says, "We could

say a warming up activity is a motivating starting point that will lead students to become animated to work efficiently in the language class” (p. 11). Group activities can reflect the practice as a beneficial one as group work is supposed to increase motivational level among students and at the same time to develop their fluency (Richards, 2006). Both fluency and motivation are two important factors of leadership learning.

4. Leadership and its Types

The development of the context of leadership, from the very introduction of this study has evolved around the global education policies, the National Curriculum of Bangladesh and the National Education Policy of Bangladesh. The policy documents very well reflected their intentions to develop the learning practice of the students. When the phrase ‘learning practice of the students’ is mentioned it reflects on quality education for students. This idea of quality education centers around creativity, critical thinking and lifelong learning which indeed is the SDG 4. The features of quality education mirror Sternberg’s (2007) leadership indicators. From here the conceptual framework for leadership from the point of view of content analysis in the EFT emerges as the capacity building among students. Capacity building from its usual perspective indicates itself to be an essential element for a sustainable and people centered development. Capacity building also stands on an act of benevolence saying ‘helping people is to help themselves’. Capacity building is ‘empowerment’, ‘participation’ and ‘gender equity’. It can ensure greater development at personal, local and national level. When this development is ensured then it creates a greater opportunity for democratization and greater accountability from the government (Eade, 1997). When capacity building from this greater perspective is minimized to skill development among students, it can reflect on the students being empowered, being more participating in helping people and community, being aware about the rights of women, and being just and enough respectful to women. Textbooks are instructed to be written on the basis of making the students more aware about the political and social history of Bangladesh, developing ethics and morality among students, making the students competent with the knowledge of modern science and technology for practical and pragmatic education, making the students as human resources to meet the global challenges, and making the students aware about the importance of gender equity (National Curriculum, Bangladesh, 2012). So, being empowered would mean students to be more professionally skilled, to be more inspired, to be self-reliant, to be more aware about human rights and responsibilities. “Empowerment is a construct that links individual strengths and competencies, natural helping systems, and proactive behaviors to social policy and social change” (Rappaport, 1981, 1984 as cited in Perkins & Zimmerman, 1997, p. 569). Being participating very often would mean to be social. Social means being ethical and moral, being altruistic (Parten, 1932). Gender equality as Sustainable Development Goal 5 elaborates is “providing women and girls with equal access to education, health care, decent work, and representation in political and economic decision-making and so on”. Among the numerous targets set by Un Women three major targets of ensuring gender equality are: (i) End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere, (ii) Eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other types of exploitation, (iii) Eliminate all harmful practices, such as child, early and forced marriage and female genital mutilation (UN, 2015). So, being respectful to women would mean them to be aware about violence against women and any sort of discrimination and social harassment against women. Now, ‘empowerment’ would be ensured when the students are inspired. Inspiration would let them be more professionally successful and motivated in terms of real life scenario. They themselves can become the

source of inspiration and motivation to others. This can give birth to the idea of Inspirational Leadership and Professional Leadership. 'Participation' as discussed above can give birth to the idea of Social Leadership. 'Gender Equality' also from the above mentioned discussion would surface as incorporated with 'empowerment' and thus Inspirational and Professional Leadership. All these three leadership ideas would be gradually discussed from the lessons of the textbook i.e. the EFT. Inspirational Leadership is drawn from the lessons dealing with famous personalities, contribution of Bangladeshi community in overseas countries and essays on peace and conflict issues and stories from myths and legends. For a better understanding of the contents, Inspirational Leadership has further been divided into Political Leadership and Leadership from Myths and Legends. Professional Leadership is drawn from the lessons to some extent on personalities, higher education and scientific achievements and inventions. Social Leadership is drawn from the lessons on etiquette and manners, human rights and contribution of teenagers as social change makers.

5. Proportion of Different Leadership Lessons in EFT

This section identifies the proportion of Inspirational Leadership, Professional Leadership and Social leadership which have been mentioned earlier in the section of Leadership and its Types. The English for Today for Classes XI & XII which is practiced and taught in the classrooms was first introduced in 2015. The book, in total has 15 units and 57 lessons. The leadership ideas are developed from the analysis based on the contents i.e. the texts in the lessons. The units and lessons had been thoroughly examined in order to extract leadership information. Even the sentences and words have been seen with a keen purpose. When leadership information is mentioned, it is being viewed as evidences emerging from the textbook.

Table 1: Number of Lessons on Leadership in EFT

Serial	Units	Number of Lessons	Individual Lessons Related to Leadership Abilities
1	Unit One: People or Institutions Making History	3	1,2,3
2	Unit Two: Traffic Education	4	0
3	Unit Three: Food Adulteration	2	0
4	Unit Four: Human Relationships	3	1
5	Unit Five: Adolescence	5	5
6	Unit Six: Path to Higher Education	3	3
7	Unit Seven: Human Rights	5	1,2,3,4,5
8	Unit Eight: Environment and Nature	5	
9	Unit Nine: Myths and Literature	4	3,4
10	Unit Ten: Dreams	3	3
11	Unit Eleven: Diaspora	4	2
12	Unit Twelve: Peace and Conflict	5	2,5
13	Unit Thirteen: Greatest Scientific Achievements	4	1,2,3,4,
14	Unit Fourteen: Art and Music	3	0
15	Unit Fifteen: Tours and Travels	4	0
Total	15	57	21

Table 2: Number of Lessons Related to Different Leadership Types

Leadership types		Units	Lessons	Total no. of lessons
Inspirational Leadership	Political leadership	1	1,2	6
		10	3	
		11	2	
		12	1,4	
	Leadership from myths and legends	9	3,4	2
Professional leadership		1	3	6
		6	3	
		13	1,2,3,4	
Social leadership		4	1	7
		5	5	
		7	1,2,3,4,5	
Total				21

The above analysis identifies how the leadership contents are incorporated in the EFT (XI-XII). Out of the total 57 lessons in the EFT, 21 lessons contain different leadership ideas. Among these 21 lessons, 6 are based on political leadership contents, 2 are based on myths and legends. While 6 are based on professional leadership ideas, the remaining 7 are based on social leadership contents for the students to learn and practice. 36 lessons are remaining neutral considered against the background of leadership aspects

Figure 1

Proportion of Lessons (among 21) According to Different Leadership Types

5.1 Inspirational Leadership

Inspirational Leadership is often proposed as a subfactor of transformational leadership which focuses on energizing a team by injecting a vision among the individuals, making them hungry for a common dream and thus showing confidence among the team members (Bass, 1985 as cited in Joshi, Lazarova & Liao, 2009). Inspirational Leadership as a radical theory of leadership bases on leadership practices of greatest world leaders of all time (Secretan, 1999). So, Inspirational Leadership, simply put is the power or capacity of inspiring others. Lessons in the EFT regarding Inspirational Leadership have created opportunity for students to learn from the lives of famous political and social activists which give rise to the Political Leadership orientation for the students. There are lessons on legendary tales from Greek mythologies which have been included as a part of Leadership from Myths and Legends. These sources of Greek tales can make the students more inquisitive and courageous.

5.1.1 Political leadership

Political leadership as Masciulli, Molchanov and Knight (2009) cites (Blondel 1987; Wildavsky 2006; Wildavsky 1989; Klenke 1996) is quite difficult to define because it depends on institutional, cultural and historical contexts and situations. It is also being said “political leadership and followership account for significant differences across and within individual nation states in responding to both newer global problems and traditional governance issues” (Masciulli et al., 2009, p. 1). Political leadership, in the text is basically presented through personalities, Bangladeshi community’s contribution in overseas countries and through essays on peace and conflict. Three most important lessons in this regard are on the lives and works of Nelson Mandela, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman and Martin Luther King Jr. These lessons are firsthand experience opportunities for the students to learn how these world famous leaders came to the rescue of their people and community.

In this global village of today this is quite normal for people and communities to live as diasporas in different countries. But leaving one’s motherland and starting a new life in another country is always challenging. A strong community leadership is needed in this regard. The lesson entitled as ‘Banglatown’ in East London” tells in brief the history of people from Bangladesh settling in England over more than half a century and how this community is enjoying their democratic rights as a very important part of England. “In 2001 British Bangladeshi leaders, including many of the second-generation activists, led a successful bid via the Tower Hamlets council to gain the official designation of ‘Banglatown’ for Brick Lane and its surrounding neighbourhoods” (EFT, 2015, p. 136). What the lesson clearly reflects is the sentiment of Bangladeshis to teach their sons and daughters about the culture and heritage of the land of their ancestors. At the same time this type of a lesson provides an experience for our local students to think beyond their own country and develop their vision as a global citizen and also teaches them to be confident enough to keep their own identity intact and high crossing the border of their own country. Coming to the issue of peace and conflict, the students from the text can learn about how world communities are working to minimize conflict and to create an environment where a war over political or economical interest is a distant possibility. “Peace movement is basically an all-encompassing anti-war movement” (EFT, 2015, p. 161).

5.1.2 Leadership from Myths and Legends

Professor Emily Anhalt (2017) with her experience of more than 30 years draws a sparkling relation between ancient legends and modern leadership:

Centuries ago, myths helped the Greeks learn to reject tyrannical authority and identify the qualities of good leadership. As I write in my book “Enraged,” the same myths that long predate the world’s very first democracy have lessons for us today – just as they did for the ancient Greeks centuries ago.

Lesson 3 & 4 of Unit 9 in the EFT are stories of *Gazi Pir* and Hercules. *Gazi Pir* was a muslim saint who came to preach Islam in the southern part of Bangladesh close to the edge of Sundarbans. Legends claim that he had miraculous power. He fought fierce animals to save loves of local community and enabled villagers to live close to forests and jungles and cultivate their lands (p. 116). Hercules is known in the Greek mythology for his ‘twelve labours’. These are all stories of bravery and chivalry which stamped Hercules’ authority as a hero possessing immense strength throughout the world (p. 119). These lessons are not supposed to make a student a hero overnight but at least they are source of inspiration as legends, myths and stories have always worked as tonics in crisis to attain courage

5.2 Professional Leadership

Professional leadership most often is the formal part of leadership. It is all about setting the mission and vision of an organization, creating a process for achieving the organizational goals and about aligning the process and procedures regarding the achievement of the goal (Mastrangelo et al., 2004). When an individual student's career success is meant, it becomes his/her own goals and the process of achieving that goal. The achievement of that goal should come through education. Education most often paves the way for successful career and thus allows a student to be professionally successful and thus become a future leader. Dugan (2006), cited (Astin & Astin, 2000; Burkhardt & Zimmerman-Oster, 1999; Council for the Advancement of Standards in Higher Education [CAS], 1999; Zimmerman-Oster & Burkhardt, 1999) saying "From both historical and contemporary perspectives, the education and development of future leaders has served as a core function of higher education (p. 217). Unit 1, Lesson 3: Two women, pp. 12-16 is remarkably important for students as it exhibits professional success concerning the fact that it exhibits women's capacity of career success to highest. It tells the stories of two female astronauts: Valentina Tereshkova and kalpana Chawla and sets examples in front of the students especially the female students to dream to the ultimate to become as legendary as them. This dream does not mean that every girl becomes an astronaut, but at least can hope for a better future for her. That can be social change making as women in Bangladesh in some cases still do not enjoy gender equality in terms of progress, empowerment and social voice. "Good governance, gender equality and women's empowerment are necessary conditions for the reduction of poverty" (Ara & Khan 2005 as cited in Kabir, Aziz and Shathi, 2018, p. 25). Professional success is hard to achieve without higher education. Lesson 3 in Unit 6 tells about the importance of 21st century higher education. This lesson guides the students with the skills which can enable them become competitive citizens of global economy. These skills will increase their ability, employability and readiness for citizenship. Five major skills are incorporated in this regard: thinking critically and making the best use of the barrage of information, solving complex multidisciplinary problems, creativity and entrepreneurial thinking skill, communicating and collaborating, and making innovative use of knowledge, information and opportunities (EFT, pp. 76-77). This is clearly in line with the idea illustrated in the national curriculum 2012 especially the curriculum of English language teaching view to developing quality education focusing on creativity, critical thinking and lifelong learning (p. 25). The textbook directly says as the including sentence of the lesson, "These skills will prepare everyone to prepare for the challenges of the 21st century and contribute to the country's development" (EFT, p. 77). Here lies the indication for effective leadership. A true leader in his/her respective field is supposed to contribute more effectively and passionately for the development of his country. Patriotism and leadership often stand complementary to each other. Patriotism as an ideal invokes citizens to give their best for the development of the country. Leadership when related to patriotism emerges as a belief for people that a cause for the country is greater than personal thoughts and interests. (Odukoya, 2017). Unit 13 with all its lessons discuss about greatest achievements in medical science, landing on the moon, revolution in information technology, space science and engineering and so on. These are all examples for the students. When in 2020, a global pandemic called Covid-19 is threatening humanity and in such a scenario if it happens that a student from Bangladesh vows to become a medical scientist and invents a cure for deadly pandemics and contributes to save precious human lives, would not that be an example of leadership? Leadership does not confine to any limited definition. It is rather inherent in action and contribution. "Great leaders are individuals who have a great vision that will benefit humanity, are committed to achieving it with integrity

and honesty, and persist in their efforts with compassion and courage despite seemingly insurmountable obstacles” (Krieger, 2008, para. 6).

5.3 Social Leadership

Social leadership is an encapsulating attitude towards building up a mind set and skill focusing on a particular social age. It is more about what a person shares and how a person shares to create his/her own reputation rather than creating any authority. It is always a whole hearted effort for community development which always remains the core concept of social leadership (Stodd, 2014). When talking about social leadership building among teen agers Price-Mitchell (2011) speaks for five steps of engaging youth in leadership development. The steps are: (i) connecting to others in need, (ii) confronting moral dilemmas, (iii) reflecting on values, (iv) shifting perspectives, (v) creating a passionate civic identity. She also comments that becoming an active citizen for children does not happen by chance. It requires proper guidance and care by parents, educators and other adults familiar with the children. These are the things which have been aligned with the lessons of EFT here in this section. A good leader is needs to have a good sense of etiquette and manners. Good leaders today, know very well about the importance of good manners in different situations and contexts. If a person is considered a good leader in his/her workplace, it does not mean that his/her leadership resulted from patterned niceness, rather from the appreciation of his/her colleagues (Hesselbein, 1997). Developing a sense of good behavior starts very early even from home and then when a child starts going to school. Children belonging to different countries and societies have different forms of etiquette and manners. S/he is needs to learn about it in the family and form educational institution. This is what we find in the words of Price-Mitchell (2011) as she speaks of cultivating values and civic identity among her teenage students. In Lesson 1, Unit 4, p.40 students are shown some features of different etiquette and manner which is presented below in a tabular form:

Table 3: *Types of Etiquettes*

Type of etiquette	Leadership orientation
Family etiquette	Respect each other's belonging
	Do not shout at children
	Listen to your parents
Basic social etiquette	Always be on time. Showing up late is a lack of respect to other people's time
	Give and receive complements graciously
Professional etiquette	Dress properly
	Never take credit for other people's work

Lesson 5, Unit 5 (pp. 64-67) provides best example of community development contribution made by some yond kinds and teenagers. Dylan Mahalingam, Alexandra Scott, Ryan Hreljac, Katie Stagliano and Anne Frank are the heroes in this lesson. Their stories can be some best examples to illustrate leadership for the students concerned with the textbook i.e. the students of HSC level in Bangladesh. Throughout the analysis a conscious effort have been given to make a juxtaposition of leadership elements in the EFT here and how the elements of leadership can inspire the students. But, what actually is leadership. It is being claimed that in English language over 10000 books and articles have been written on leadership. But there is not one universally accepted definition of leadership. However, leadership can be called as a kind of persuasion, a kind of influence which inspires people to work for a common goal

which is relevant to a group (Pfeiffer & Wechsler, 2013). Getting a little deviated from the definition, leadership can be understood not as persuasion but as setting examples and leaving trails for people to follow those examples. A leader can leave the choice for people.

Unit 7 with all its lessons (pp. 79-90) make the students learn about human rights. With some very small pieces of contents in the lessons, it has spoken about human rights, violation happening across the world. It has also spoken about some of the articles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and has associated different group and individual activities as exercises for the students. This process in itself is a very effective technique of making students aware of human rights and at the same time their own rights and responsibilities. "When students study about people and communities throughout the world as well as their strengths and needs, the learning process becomes more personal and pertinent, and the foreign becomes more familiar" (Hawkins & Knox, 2014, p. 249). Ultimately this practice indeed appears to be a practice of leadership skills because a leader or even a common citizen deserves to know about the basic human rights. A leader can truly perform and practice the leadership duties only when s/he knows what the rights of people are and what for a leader is supposed to fight.

So, when human rights have been integrated into the boundary of social leadership, the intention is to align it again with the National Curriculum 2012 and the National Education Policy 2010. As social work is increasingly developing as an international phenomenon educational approaches need to be more congenial to integrate this content into curriculum. Developing social leadership is then incorporated with the theme of universal human rights. This is an encouragement for the students to analyze oppressive practices of power and to pursue equality for all people through acquiring human rights literacy (knowledge), empathy (values), responsibility (action), and transforming this into global leadership (change) (Hawkins & Knox, 2014). Bangladesh, with the curriculum and education policy seems to appear very well accommodating in this aspect as has been mentioned and cited in the earlier section of Leadership and its Types (National Curriculum Bangladesh, 2012).

6. The Exercises of the Lessons and Practicing Leadership through CLT

An elaborative analysis has already been presented as the relation of CLT with leadership and the leadership types emerging from the EFT. This process in itself has shown how the contents in the EFT can help the students to culture leadership abilities getting inspiring ideas from the EFT. But how they can, specifically, practice some of the traits of leadership in the classroom is quite related to the patterns of exercises in the lessons. Teachers are to facilitate the learning process by making the students participate in the exercises. The study has also discussed what the major activities in a CLT classroom are and how these activities can facilitate leadership abilities. Keeping in line with the previous findings, in most of the lessons exercises which can relate to leadership are based on warm up activities, group works and project presentations. At the same time CLT being a more balanced approach of language teaching always encourages oral or spoken contributions from students. Richards (2006) has affirmed some core assumptions related with current CLT that gives emphasis on developing speaking skill through engaging learners in interaction and meaningful communication in the second language. He calls for a communicative competence which means learners are encouraged to communicate according to the context. Communicative competence is related to oratory and oratory to leadership. For most people, the charismatic leader is a spellbinding, or at least a highly effective orator (Bryman, 1992). Unit 1, Lesson 2, pp. 6-11

showing a picture asks the students to discuss among themselves about the historic 7 March Speech of Bangabandhu. Then there is again a project work to make a presentation on how the speech became a part of the history of Bangladesh. It also tells the students to make a fact file on the life of Bangabandhu. These are all learning opportunities for the students through the exercises. Unit 9, Lesson 3, p. 120 asks the students to write a paragraph of about 150 words on a heroic man or woman that they have heard or read about in their childhood. Then as a follow-up activity in the form of group presentation asks the students to prepare brief presentations on a few Bangladeshi heroes famous for their fighting abilities. Unit 1, Lesson 3, p. 15 includes an exercise saying "Who are some of the famous women in your country and why are they famous?" So, all these are examples of exercises (with so many more in different lessons) which give a picture of classroom practices for the students. It then rests on the teachers how they can engage and motivate the students. "It goes without saying that teachers are an ultimate key, if not the key, to successful education and that they play a vital role in bringing about educational reform" (Hargreaves & Fullan, 1992; Suwande, 1995 as cited in Birjandi & Bagherkazemi, 2010, p. 135).

7. Conclusion

As an analysis of the EFT as the major document of this study, the findings reveal the amount, proportion and effect of leadership contents in the text book. The findings suggest that the book has created a very well opportunity for the students to learn about leadership. The leadership lessons have been categorized thematically into four types and then respective lessons coming under the specific leadership theme have been elaborately discussed to find out the association and practice of that very leadership skill for the students. There has been a parallel presentation of accepted and established leadership literatures to validate the usefulness of the contents in the textbook. At the same time the study reveals CLT's possible effective contribution to make the students practice the skills of leadership. It would not be unjustified in this regard to opine that as an approach of English language teaching and as an approach to assist leadership learning CLT appears to be best suited. As the present curriculum and the national education policy of Bangladesh focus on building global citizens through quality education, it is not possible without nurturing the students as future leaders. When speaking about them as future leaders, it does not mean leadership just from its textual meaning. It goes beyond. This leadership is about being a visionary, being a successful professional, being a person who learns to be selfless, learns to be humane and thus contribute for the development of the country to the ultimate limit. The study is just a small venture in this regard. As a triangle of leadership contents in the text book, their impact on the students, and CLT's role in ensuring the leadership practice, this study is just the presentation of the existing scenario. But this is believed to open the window of reflection of what the two bibles in form of the curriculum and national education policy intended; how far the textbook has been able to hold the intentions and how the teachers have been able to implement the practice through English language teaching in the classrooms. Opportunity awaits for more to be added in the noble goal of creating every student of Bangladesh a leader and an asset to the country.

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